

1 Cadherin 2 expression during TE lineage specification in an iPS model of lineage commitment in the
2 human embryo.

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 Cdh2 as a lineage commitment cooperating factor or marker of the lineage commitment program in
10 embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Nani, D., Alvizi, L., de Siqueira Bueno, H.M., Lacerda, E.C.M., Yan, C.Y.I. and Passos-Bueno,
13 M.R., 2025. Maternal–fetal inflammation affects Cdh1/E-cadherin epigenetic regulation and craniofacial
14 development. bioRxiv, pp.2025-09.
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28